

Isaac Chidi Igwe,

Franklin Emenike Okamigbo

RETHINKING THE IGBO METAPHYSICS OF HOME AND HOMECOMING CULTURE: THREATS AND PROSPECTS

ABSTRACT

In Martin Heidegger's philosophy, the concept of homecoming is deeply rooted in the exploration of being and authenticity. In this context, the search for authenticity is understood as a return to one's true self and an atonement to the essence of being. For the Igbo, much more than self-realization and the self-affirmative nature of homecoming as understood in Heidegger, it is a profound and purposive engagement not only with one's own existence but also the existence of the ancestral spirit embedded in home-consciousness. As such, within the Igbo understanding of homecoming lies other similar concepts like identity, authenticity, rest, truth and ownership. Therefore, for the Igbo, home is a fundamental cultural rite that defines and completes an Igbo person in the eyes of the globe. Beyond ancestral sentimentality, the culture fosters unity and reconnection between the rural and the diaspora dwellers. This regular communion between the city and the village spreads development and sustains the life of rural economy, without which the ancestral home would be desolate. With this, the homecoming culture achieves one of the critical components of Sustainable Development Goals, which aims at promoting economic growth and social inclusion. Regrettably, with the aid of phenomenology, the paper observes that the prospect of this cherished social intercourse appears challenged in many parts of the Igbo society. Findings identify these challenges to include: concern for safety, cultural globalization and the thinking that cultures evolve, and as such, homecoming has become obsolete. Moving forward, the paper contends that the essence of cultural evolution is progress, and any cultural practice with demonstrable capacity to midwife progress, such as the homecoming culture, ought not be abandoned as obsolete. It concludes that without the sustenance of the homecoming culture the Igbo race would become soulless and would deprive the race the benefits of social intercourse between diaspora and rural dwellers.

Keywords: Metaphysics, Igbo, Home-Consciousness, Homecoming Culture, Ancestral-root

INTRODUCTION

The idea of metaphysics in philosophy refers to a doctrine of reality; that is, a study of what is, insofar as it is¹. It is a branch of philosophy that explores fundamental questions about the nature of reality (whether it is tangible or intangible), existence (whether or not it precedes essence²), and the relationship between mind and matter. In the modern era, philosophers like René Descartes and Immanuel Kant contributed to metaphysical discussions, addressing issues such as substance, causation, and the nature of knowledge. In contrast, postmodern perspectives, emerging in the twentieth century, challenge traditional metaphysical assumptions. Thinkers like Jacques Derrida and Michel Foucault questioned the possibility of objective truth and emphasized the role of language in shaping or understanding of reality. Postmodern metaphysics often involves deconstruction, highlighting the fluidity and subjectivity of concepts.

While modern metaphysics sought universal truth, postmodernism embraces diversity and acknowledges the influence of language and culture on our perception of reality. The interplay between these contrasting views continues to shape contemporary metaphysical discussions.

On a similar plane, there is cultural metaphysics or metaphysics of culture, which provides an analysis of concepts and practices uniquely wrapped within a distinctive culture of the world. It pries into the life-world and method of interpretation of experience and all that belongs to cultural specifics; including persons, artworks, language, history, patterns of behaviour, institutions and norms.³ It emphasizes the historical character of human thinking and engagement. Reinforcing this view, John Falk in the article “The Role of Cultural Metaphysics in Psychological Theory” agrees that every civilization has certain basic assumptions about how reality is structured. These assumptions which become somewhat apparent when examining the different language groups,

¹ Coreth, E. *Metaphysics*, (New York: Herder, 1968), pp-17-30

² Panrleon Iroegbu, *Metaphysics, the Kpim of Philosophy*, (Owerri: International University Press, 1995), pp.48-49.

³ Joseph Margolis, *Towards a Metaphysics of Culture*, 1st Edition (London: Routledge, 2019)

make up a system of cultural metaphysics.⁴ Therefore, I make bold to say that it is within this corridor of metaphysical discourse that the theme of this paper can be identified.

Martin Heidegger, on his part, calls human attention to the need to treat metaphysics as ontology⁵ and, this forms the central theme of his philosophical work. He contends that traditional metaphysics, which focuses on abstract concepts and general principles, overlooks the fundamental nature of being. Heidegger seeks to redirect metaphysical inquiry from abstract concepts to an exploration of the nature of being-in-the-world. In “Being and Time”, he emphasizes the existential aspect of ontology, emphasizing human existence (Dasein) and its engagement with the world. He challenges the idea that being can be reduced to mere presence and encourages a more phenomenological engagement with concrete and lived experience of being.

In line with the directive for metaphysics to explore human lived experience rather than dwell on abstract theorization, which keeps roving like barber’s chair, this paper grounds what it describes as homecoming culture, a lived experience of the Igbo people. This metaphysics of man reveals a cultural being whose part of ontological feature entails continued social intercourse between the self and the ancestral root. The paper attempts to show how such cultural practice contributes in shaping the reality of the Igbo people. In the same vein, it also throws up some existential threats to the continuity of this edifying culture.

PERSPECTIVES IN THE CONCEPT OF HOME

The very idea of home is complex and multidimensional. Different social issues appear to influence and shape opinions on what constitutes home. To some people, it signifies a shelter or a building edifice constructed either as a temporal or permanent place of residence. In various literature, home is sometimes related to a building, house, heaven or haven. Sociology, psychology, anthropology, history and philosophy have different accounts on what constitutes home⁶. Because it has been approached from different perspectives by several scholars, the concept of home has always had several layers of complexity.

⁴ John L, Falk, “The Role of Cultural Metaphysics in Psychological Theory” in *Canadian Journal of Psychology*, vol 7 (1), 1953 available @<https://psycnet.apa.org/buy/1954-00044-001>

⁵ Jim Unah, *Metaphysics*, (Lagos: University of Lagos Press, 2010), pp.136-137.

⁶ Shelley Mallett, Understanding Home: A Critical Review of the Literature. *The Sociological Review*, Volume 52, Issue 1, (Melbourne: University of Melbourne, 2004), p.62

Notwithstanding, for the majority of individuals on earth, the connotations associated with the word *home* are the most consoling and relaxing. A person's mental state of stability and acceptance is evoked by the word *home*, which denotes a secure and cozy place. The majority of human memories are created at home, and for many people, home is more of an emotion than a physical location.

While re-echoing the views of Macy Douglas, Study Corgi, posits that the concept of home has both positive and negative connotations, depending on who is doing the assessment. According to him, for most young people, the notion of home resonates a place of tyranny of parenthood. Home for them evokes the memory of entrapped freedom and therefore wish to escape the control and scrutiny of parents. "The combination of nostalgia and resistance to rule that exist in people's homes is an interesting mixture"⁷ which combines to shape the idea of home for different classes of human beings.

The conclusion drawn from the above observation by Douglas is that the question of home ought not to be defined by its function. In other words, Corgi writes: "this means that home does not provide the ultimate care for people and represents a space with very specific characteristics that are complicated to define and describe"⁸. Corgi further explains that Douglas's intention in his assessment of home is to say that "home is not necessarily a fixed space...home does not always need to be made of bricks and mortar; it can be a tent in the middle of a desert, a boat on the shore of a lake, a wagon in a trailer park"⁹. Another thing which does not matter in what constitutes a home is the size or the space it occupies. Nevertheless, there should be "a certain sense of regularity that gives people a certain level of comfort and confidence"¹⁰, although this again will depend on who is evaluating what constitutes comfort and confidence. To some people, home is that place where they return to each day after going out to look for daily bread.

Corgi, again compares the views of Douglas about home with that of Bell Hook, stating that while Douglas's approach focuses predominantly on the concept of home as a feeling and sense of belonging, Hook ascribes more

⁷ Study Corgi, *what is 'home': Personal Idea and Scholar's Approaches to the Definition of 'home'*. November 11, 2023, Retrieved from <https://studycorgi.com/what-is-home/>

⁸ *ibid*

⁹ *ibid*

¹⁰ *ibid*

tangible characteristics to home. His description of home evokes a sense of safety, and homecoming a sense of completeness¹¹.

While airing what he calls his personal views, Corgi writes that a home should not be associated with just material object or intangible emotions. Rather, to build one's own sense of home, a person should consider the interplay between tangible items and the feelings they arouse. He further states that, for certain individuals, the existence of family defines home. To them, home exists wherever family resides. He notes that home could be in a quaint old house with the family gathered around the table, or it could be in the midst of a forest while camping with friends and family.¹² Some perspectives see it as an assortment of items that provide solace and aid in unwinding following a demanding workday. As a result, each individual defines home differently depending on what is important, cozy and meaningful to them.

Heidegger's concept of "building" and "dwelling" is central to his philosophy. In "Building, Dwelling Thinking", he explores the idea of home as complex relationship between humans and their environment. For him, building is not just constructing physical structures but also the process of creating a space where human existence unfolds.

"Dwelling" goes beyond the mere act of residing; it involves an intimate connection with the environment. Heidegger emphasizes the importance of dwelling in a way that respects the essence of a place, acknowledging its uniqueness and allowing it to reveal itself. The idea of home, then, is not merely a shelter but a harmonious integration with the surrounding world. It is for this reason that he criticizes modern technology and industrialization for disrupting this relationship by reducing spaces to mere resources. In Heidegger's view, genuine dwelling involves a thoughtful engagement with the environment, fostering a sense of belonging and atonement to the world.

In essence, Heidegger's concept of home transcends the physical structure, emphasizing a deep, meaningful connection between humans and their environment, urging a more mindful and harmonious approach to dwelling. In other words, he seems to agree with the majority view that a home is a place which evokes a sense of completeness, harmony, and where the universals and particulars are reconciled.

¹¹ *ibid*

¹² *ibid*

THE HOME IN IGBO BELIEF

The Igbo people, whose cultural specific (homecoming) this article is dedicated to, form one of the three populous cultural groups in Nigeria, and are majorly located in the southeastern part of the country. Rightly captured in Okoye and Ukanwa, for administrative calibration, the Igbo people are made up of “the entire Omambala (Anambra), Abia, Ebonyi, Enugwu and Imo states, parts of Delta and Rivers State.”¹³ We should also add here that the Igbo people are found in some parts of Benue, Kogi and Cross Rivers States. Apart from aboriginal population of Igbo people occupying the above mentioned places, there is a large number of Igbo people outside their autochthonous habitat. In fact, in every state of Nigeria, after the indigenous or ethnic population, the Igbo people are usually the second largest population. Outside Nigeria, the Igbo people also have large populations in many countries of the world. This has led to the comic saying that: “If you get to any part of the world and don’t find Igbo people there, please run away from that place”¹⁴ because it means that such place may not be habitable to humankind.

While agreeing with Corgi and the like as to what a home is (a place of succour, safety and hope), the Igbos, much more than Corgi, understand the concept of home to transcend a mere physical structure often described as house. It is a place of identity, a sanctuary where roots run deep. It is a confluence of an unbroken circle of the living, the dead, and yet unborn. It is in the light of this understanding that the idea of home is hierarchicalized. In other words, Igbo people can build and have homes or residence in several places in the cities all over the world, live there with their families, yet there is this “other sense of home” which continues to inundate their consciousness all through their entire existence. This “other sense of home” is, however, of two dimensions and the duo are understood as ancestral homes. The first category exists in space and time while the second category is timeless (the spirit world) and transcends location. Still, it is believed that one’s relationship with the former determines one’s eligibility for the latter because the former is where the being and whole essence of the Igbo person takes root. The former refers to the terrestrial autochthonous or allochthonous home within which the family, clan or

¹³ Chidimma Okoye and Obinna Ukanwa, “Igbo Traditional Architecture: A Symbol of Igbo Cultural Identity” in *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research* Volume 10, Issue 11, November-2019 <http://www.ijser.org>

¹⁴ Azuka Onwuka, “How ‘Village’ has Harmed the Igbo People” in *The Punch Newspapers*, 9th January 2024. https://punchng-com.translate.google.com/how-village-has-harmed-the-igbo-people/?_x_tr_sl=en&_x_tr_tl=ig&_x_tr_hl=ig&_x_tr_pto=sc

community history revolves while the latter is the spirit world, inhabited by the deceased family members. Although these family members may be dead, they are believed to be part of the earthly family and in constant relationship with those they left behind. For this reason, both realms of home are summarily understood as ancestral home. Again, both notions of homes have harmonious and reciprocal relationships because one needs the other to remain causally relevant in the family/community chain of meaningfulness.

Therefore, arising from the above conceptualization, the utmost idea of home for the Igbos is the ancestral home, in whatever form the term is understood. The adjective “ancestral”, used in qualifying the concept of home is fundamentally significant in Igbo social/family ontology. To be sure, Ancestors in Igbo metaphysics is other wise known as *Ndichie*. They are people in the society who led good and admirable life while they were alive in the physical world and are believed to continue their existence after death in the spirit world. J.S Mbiti, describes them as the “Living-dead”¹⁵.

Again, Nwafor Ikechukwu further explains that “These living-dead are always involved in the affairs of their families on earth, assisting them in their struggles and warning them of any impending danger in their family life.”¹⁶ In this manner, they have dual nature and language. In other words, they can wear the body of a living family person when they want to carry out certain assignments and they can also exist in disembodied form. Consequently, they can speak the language of the living and that of the dead. This position is corroborated by Mbiti in the following words: “But the living-dead are bilingual: they speak the language of men, with whom they lived until ‘recently’; and they speak the language of the spirits and of God, to whom they are drawing nearer ontologically.”¹⁷ In addition, Madukasi has it that “Ancestors can be highly localized, that is when there are ancestors for a whole community or many homes or a whole tribe. There are ancestors for family.”¹⁸

¹⁵ J.S. Mbiti, *African Religions and Philosophy*, (London: Heinemann, 1985) pp.83-275.

¹⁶ Ikechukwu M. Nwafor, “The living-dead (ancestors) among the Igbo-African people: An interpretation of Catholic sainthood” in *International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*, vol.9 (4), p.37, 2017. DOI: 10.5897/IJSA2017.0719

¹⁷ J.S. Mbiti, Op. Cit.

¹⁸ Chuks Madukasi, “Obu” The Sacred Homestead for Ancestral Veneration” in *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, Vol.5 Issue(1), 2021, p.469
www.rsisinternational.org

Like many other African societies, this belief in ancestorship defines and permeates the Igbo concept of home as that state of autochthony without which the Igbo person becomes soulless. The notion of ancestral home for the Igbos is anchored on the concept of *Obi/Obu*. Every Igbo person has an *Obi* or *Obu* which is located at the ancestral home. *Obu* or *Obi* is a sacred place of purity, peace and justice. It is like the modern day boardroom, meeting centre or family chambers within the family compound where guests are received, family decisions are made, and connection between the members of the family and their departed family ancestors becomes deeply *felt*. It comes with varieties of nomenclature in various Igbo societies but its significance and symbolism remain the same. For the Ezza people of Ebonyi state, it is known by the name *Okpoku*. There is feeling of spiritual connectivity and social bonding when congregated in the *Obi* or *Okpoku*. According to Igbo History and Facts, “the *Obi* is also symbolic; it functions as the tempo-spiritual essence of the collective identity of an Igbo household.”¹⁹

Along the foregoing line of thought, the Igbo’s cognitive engagement with supernatural reality is mediated by their existential realism in an enclave called Nigeria. Their constantly changing experiences continue to reshape and re-enforce their perception and unified consciousness of membership of a distinct ethnic nationality other than the artificially created Nigerian state. As a result, their existential reality and cultural objects, that is, the ancestral reality and the place of *Obi*, rely on their conceptual resources which have continued to outlive the changing times. Therefore, at the heart of the homecoming practice is the Igbo belief in the spiritual significance of ancestral veneration (not worship), Igbos do not worship their ancestors. Rather, they honour them because they hold a deep respect for their family lineage. Returning home presents ample opportunities of visiting ancestral graves, making prayer requests at grave sides, and participating in family rituals. These actions are so symbolic because they reinforce the bond between the living and the living-dead, ensuring a sustained chain of blessing from one generation to the other.

¹⁹ This definition is extracted from a thread on a X-handle “Igbo History & Facts”, titled *The Importance of “Obi” in Igbo Land*. Posted on December 5th, 2020

HOMEcoming CULTURE AMONG THE IGBO PEOPLE: PUSH AND PULL

To be sure, Igbo culture speaks of the customs, tradition and practices of the Igbo people. This cuts across age-long practices and newly evolved concepts which have been inculcated into the culture of the people. The ashes and ruins of the civil war herald symbolic consciousness of the ancestral home and constantly reminds the Igbos of a nation in search of self-realisation and affirmation. The civil war memory reinforces their attachment to the ancestral home. Being reduced to near level zero by the post war policies and realities of the Nigerian State, the few that were left alive, crept out of their holes and were forced to re-embrace the same country that had massacred them for unjustifiable reasons. Emerging from this mood of despair, the Igbos picked up their broken pieces, and sojourned to several parts of the world in droves in search of hope. For them, deep down in their consciousness, “home was where to refuge and live, or come back to rest and die, in peace. The home was where they couldn’t flee from and abandon.”²⁰ So, in the views of Ugoji Egbujo, it then became imperative for the Igbos that their wealth must come home to receive validation since wealth stored outside might end up becoming abandoned property, as the after-war experience revealed.

Egbujo, again, reiterates the position that the war made home the place of last resort in the face of rejection, since the question of full integration into the Nigerian system continues to beg for answers. The point to drive home here is; although homecoming is a fundamental cultural practice for the Igbos, it became more widely accepted and practiced due to the feeling of non-acceptance into the Nigerian state, postwar. This turn out of event rekindled their love for ancestral home as a place of last resort when the push comes to shove. In fact, the uniqueness of the Igbo people’s attachment to home and homecoming is manifested in time of burying their dead. Igbos do not bury their dead ones in the public cemeteries (although there could be few exceptions due to contact with foreign cultures), nor do they bury the dead in township outside the homeland, even when the deceased might have built and lived in a mansion of his own in the town while alive. They seem to be one of the few, if not the only, tribe in Nigeria who engage in such practice of taking their dead to their homestead for internment. This practice is anchored on the belief that the spirit of the dead Igbo person does not rest until the corpse is taken home for burial in the homeland.

²⁰ Ugoji Egbujo, “The Igbo and Homecoming”. *Vanguard NewsPaper*, 13, May, 2023 available @<https://www.vanguardngr.com/2023/05/the-igbo-and-homecoming/>

At the heart of the homecoming practice is the Igbo belief in ancestral veneration (not worship), Igbos do not worship their ancestors. Rather, they honour them because they hold a deep respect for their family lineage. Returning home presents ample opportunity of visiting ancestral graves, making prayer requests at grave sides, and participating in family rituals. These actions are so symbolic because they reinforce the bond between the living and the living-dead, ensuring a sustained chain of blessing from one generation to the other.

In fact, the war and postwar experience of the Igbos, with all its ugly memories, ended up a blessing in disguise. This is because the continued refusal of the drivers of Nigeria to fully rehabilitate, reconstruct and reintegrate the Igbo people into the Nigerian state both in physical policy, power sharing and project allocation, instilled into the Igbos a strong sense of nationalism and the desire to rebuild and develop their homeland. Through this nationalistic attitude of the Igbos towards their homeland, a region that was close to been described as “desolate” after the war, has become one of the most developed communities in Nigeria, thanks to the determined efforts of the Igbo people towards not abandoning their root. In various parts of the Igbo communities, we now have modern structures that can compete with any structure in the world, all because of a people who had refused to abandon their ancestral root, all because of a rejected people who had refused to reject themselves.

A corollary to the foregoing is the consistent issuing of eviction threats and intention to kill Igbos wherever they reside. In fact, in the build up to the 2015 governorship election in Lagos state, the Oba of Lagos was quoted to have said that if the Igbos refuse to vote for his preferred candidate on the Election Day, he would drown them in the Lagos Lagoon without any consequence. He boasted that he owned Lagos and would do anything he wished²¹. In a similar circumstance, another ultimatum was issued by Arewa Consultative Youth Forum (a coalition of socio-political groups in Northern Nigeria) to the Igbos residing in the Northern parts of Nigeria to leave the region or be killed in their numbers. Furthermore, the group also threaten to take over their lands and properties after they might have driven them away. This threat was issued on June 6, 2017, and it stated that if the Igbos fail to leave the region by October 1, 2017, that maximum force would be used to evict them, including killing them.²²

²¹Ameh Comrade Godwin (6 April, 2015) “Anyone that does not vote Ambode will be thrown into lagoon-Oba of Lagos warns Igbos”. *Daily Post*, <https://dailypost.ng/2015/04/06>

²² Abdulkareem Haruna (June, 7, 2017), “Arewa Groups ask Igbos to leave Northern Nigeria, Threaten Violence”. *Premium Times*, <https://www.premiumtimesng.com>

Such threat to life and properties had been the experience of the Igbos in various parts of Nigeria where they reside, including those who reside in all the way South Africa, the xenophobic experience. This makes the thought about *home* ever-present in their consciousness. This constant reminder that the Igbos are strangers in a community they had lived for several years, built multimillion naira businesses and raised families who grew up to see that very community as their place of birth, gives a strong push to home-going consciousness. It is a double disaster for one who is rejected to turn around and reject oneself.

Besides the war experience, its aftermath realities and ancestral home sentiment, another push and pull to this cultural phenomenon orbits around the imperativeness of extending the goodies of civilization to rural dwellers by way of regularly associating with home. This culture has succeeded in fostering unity between diaspora Igbos and native homeland/rural dwellers. This continued association engenders reciprocal influence. While the diaspora dweller brings home cosmopolitan influence to the table, the native/rural dweller gives in return cultural and traditional influence. This is the reason many Igbo families have cultivated the habit of taking their children home, most especially during festivities, for cultural education and for familiarization with ancestral root. It's no surprise that despite residing in distant places, the soul of each Igbo person remains deeply connected to their ancestral homeland. This connection brings about great excitement and happiness in the households of every Igbo son and daughter when news circulates that the children of the land are preparing to embark on the lengthy and tiring journey back home to join in the celebrations that lie ahead.

The event of homecoming brings a feeling of hope and happiness to home-comers. It evokes a sense of reconnection with lost memories, lost or fading cultural/traditional knowledge, it brings together lost friendship and opportunities for family/relative familiarization. Township mode of existence in conjunction with the modern craze for privacy and individuality, destroys communitarian spirit and social solidarity. That is why two brothers can live just a pole apart in the town, yet may never see each other once in twelve calendar months. And if this could be the experience of a people who live so close to each other, imagine those who live at separate-distant location. This antithesis find synthetic expression at occasions of homecoming. It fills that vacuum created by modern feeling of loss of brotherhood embedded in township life.

Homecoming is also used by a good number of Igbo bachelors and spinsters as opportunities for discovering marriage partners. The most

scintillating of it all is homecoming during festive periods. There are traditional exhibitions, cultural dances, masquerade parades and traditional beauty pageant and wrestling. In this sense, returning home at festive times is not just about visiting, it is about reconnecting with one's root, paying homage to ancestors and reaffirming unbroken ties to family, clan and community. This mass migration also contributes significantly to boosting the local or rural economy, most especially at festive times. It makes huge impact on businesses; including transportation, hospitality, local markets and artisanship. In fact, during these periods, towns and villages become transformed into bustling hubs; the biggest beneficiaries of such moments being traders and service providers who often experience seasonal boom. Collins Onugbe's firsthand experience of this is worth sharing. In his narration, he has this to say:

I visited a shopping mall in the eastern heartland of Owerri during the Christian and new year holidays. Had wanted to shop for a few things I thought a ShopRite would be the most convenient place to pick up. But I was unable to shop. The crowd in this mall was frightening and the checkout counters had mile long queues. I could not imagine myself spending an hour to check out at the counter. Most shoppers I saw in the mall looked like those who had migrated to the East for the holidays. You could hear American accent, British accent in conversations. And see Lagos and Abuja swag in the walk of shoppers. From all over the world the Igbos had come home for Christmas. And they descended on the few shopping malls, hotels, markets in the region. There were traffic gridlocks in towns and villages. All over the East during this season, you will not miss the celebrations, the shopping, the reunion by families that mark this period among Igbo families²³.

When you merge the drive for PROGRESS with the gravitational force of HOME, you create a continually ambitious and socially adaptable population that is willing to venture anywhere for success, yet feels the necessity to return HOME to meet community responsibilities. This is

²³ Collins Onuegbu, "Travel: The Economics of Igbo Homecoming" (January, 2017) available @<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/travel-economics-igbo-homecoming-collins-onuegbu/>

illustrated by Life Lager's brand slogan: "TURU UGO LOTA" (Bring Home The Glory).²⁴

THREATS TO THE HOMECOMING CULTURE OF THE IGBO PEOPLE

The biggest threat to this celebrated cultural practice of the Igbos is the crisis of identity, which has befallen some Igbo people residing outside the homeland. Due to the rapid pace of civilization and the new dawn of the idea of global community, a good number of Igbo migrants and sojourners have become acculturated into their host communities, assimilating foreign values and languages to the extent of losing that sense of national ontological identity which makes one people uniquely different from other people. This acculturation syndrome has given birth to another disingenuous concept known as *ala bu otu* "all lands are identical" or "ontological sameness of all lands".

This concept implies that there is no ontological differentiation between one indigenous land and another. To the advocates of this concept, there is nothing significantly special about one's homeland or place of origin. In other words, wherever one resides amounts to one's homeland. It is for this reason that in the last couple of years, there had been records of some Igbos who conducted traditional marriages of their children in cities like Lagos, Abuja or other places of residence outside the native homeland. In the past, such idea was unheard of. To us here in this paper, this understanding is warped and affront to the idea of homeland and homecoming.

Unfortunately, adherents of this warped notion of homeland seem to be daily gaining momentum among handful number of diaspora Igbos. This group of individuals are in serious identity crises and are in dire need of self-discovery and identity retrieval. There is no equivocation to the fact that the fact of identity is the first principle of being. Anthony Kalu reemphasizes this view and agrees that the search for identity embodies the value expressed by one of the first principles of being. This principle holds that "every being is determined in itself, is one with itself and is consistent in itself". Therefore, every being is one in itself and divided from the others. That is to say that every being is separate from the others and the qualities of matter such as colour, size, and shape and so on

²⁴ Tosin Balogun, Why Igbos Build Mansions: A Deep Dive on Marketing, Cultural Norms of Ndigbo" available @ <https://brandcom.ng/2024/01/08/why-igbos-build-mansions-a-deep-dive-on-marketing-cultural-norms-of-ndigbo/>

distinguish the same being from the other.²⁵arguing further, he writes: if being does not have an identity, everything would be everything, giving birth to one thing since nothing can be differentiated from the other, in this case, there would be no subject and object relationship”²⁶.

Therefore, Kalu concludes that to reason along the line of non-identity of being, would create what he calls a “causal traffic in the order of being. It is on this basis that we describe believers in “ala bu otu” philosophy as ontologically displaced individuals. The truth is that the Igboland is distinct from non-Igboland, in the same way A is distinct from B. The Indians, Chinese and Jews all believe in this principle, which is the reason they usually think home, notwithstanding the amount of investments in their various places of abode. This is the reason the Chinese and Indians in particular are respected world over. They have kept faith with their cultures for centuries. They have retained their souls and resisted thoughtless modernization and the audacity of wokeism. Home must remain home for the Igbos. As noted by Egbujo, during the rainy season, the Igbos do travel home for August meetings and New Yam festivals. The trips are partly metaphysical because it is meant for renewal of the spirits with “the virginity of ruralness, filiality of kinship and melancholy of nostalgia.”²⁷

Another major threat militating against the age-long culture of homecoming of the Igbos is insecurity occasioned by full scale banditry in all parts of Igboland. In various parts of Igboland, home has been deserted because coming home has become risky for fear of kidnapping and other violent extremist activities²⁸. The elderly and the affluent who chose home for retirement have become endangered species. As rightly observed by Egbujo, men with balls now dread taking their wives and children home for Christmas to inculcate in them the homecoming culture. According to him, grown men now sneak into their ancestral homes and sleep fitfully with windows shuttered, drenched in sweat. And before dawn, before they see their umunna and reconnect with ancestral spirits, they elope to the nearest city from where they would weigh the safety of another clandestine entry.

²⁵ Anthony Kalu, African Identity and the Emergence of Globalization” in *American International Journal of Contemporary Research* Vol. 3 No. 6; June 2013, p.34

²⁶ *ibid*

²⁷ Ugoji Egbujo, “The Igbo and Homecoming”. *Vanguard NewsPaper*, op.cit

²⁸ Isaac Igwe, “Combating Radicalism and Violent Extremism in Local Communities: Perspectives and Practices” in *NARC JOURNAL* Vol. 4, N0.1 (Abuja: Nigerian Army Resource Center, 2021), pp.116-117

The fear of home has become an existential threat to the Igbo nation, no thanks to the activities of masquerading and pretentious freedom fighters²⁹, majority of whom are share criminals usurping the Biafran noble course. Huge investments that could have been domiciled within southeastern states are now taken to neighbouring regions for fear of violent extremist activities. Egbujo, again, deposits that since home has turned into a place of fear, the relationship between the diaspora and their homeland has become tense. Children of the diaspora are realizing that home is a perilous place. If they reach adulthood with this perception, they will lack the reasons to cherish home as their fathers did. When people abandon their homeland, the rural economy collapses. He warns that “without money and jobs, and without the motivation that city people bring back with their success stories, the village youth take to yahoo yahoo , drugs and crimes”.³⁰.

EVALUATION AND CONCLUSION

In the face of a new social order occasioned by globalization and urbanization and the attendant involuntary ways of reshaping lives and changing values, the culture of homecoming invokes a strong reminder of the imperativeness of heritage preservation and cultural identity. The Igbo homecoming culture need not lose its steeze and grandeur in the face of the audacity of wokeism. Igbo parents and custodians of Igbo traditions and values should continue to ensure that the younger generation of Igbo people, many of whom are born and raised outside the ancestral community, remain in touch with their ancestral roots for the sake of identity preservation. To reinforce this advocacy, there is a sad story of a young city girl who unknowingly got entangled in an amorous affair with her first cousin, and this love affair resulted in pregnancy; they both settled for marriage. It was now time for the suitor to take the fiancée to his native town and introduce her to family members, as custom of the Igbos; ironically, an ugly incident ensued. This ugly incident that unfolded was that the man whom the suitor introduced the fiancée to as his father was indeed an uncle to the fiancée. As a matter of fact, the parents of the girl had not came home when the girl was a child, and since then, they had remained in the city. They were not privy to the marriage arrangement between their daughter and a guy she found in the city (because they girl was scared of letting her parents know that she was pregnant without marriage). When the reality dawned on her that she had all this while fallen in love, and in earnest been impregnated by the

²⁹ *ibid*

³⁰ *ibid*

son of her father's younger brother, she became indignant at the action of her parents for refusing to bring her home, constantly, to reconnect with her roots and family members. Of course, in Igbo traditions and culture, their act was a taboo. But it was avoidable, had the parents imbued and sustained the homecoming culture. This case study, again, reinforces the need to preserve this cultural practice.

The argument sustained in this work is that without homecoming, the Igbo ancestral home will become overrun by thorny weeds. Egbujo maintains this belief in his view that it is the unbroken social intercourse between the diaspora and the ancestry that motivates and reinvents the Igbo spirit. The importance of home and home consciousness for the Igbos cannot be over emphasized. If the Igbos will ever get it right in their relationship with the outside world, most especially with the conglomerate called Nigeria, they must get it right from home because charity they say begins at home. Certain humiliations faced by the Igbo outside the southeastern region reflect the chaos and lack of unity of purpose back home. Back home, there is cold tension in the relationship between Imo state Igbos versus their Anambra counterparts. The same feeling of disgruntlement is nursed by those from Ebonyi state who are pejoratively and summarily profiled as "Abakaleke people" by their sister Igbo people from other states. The feeling of inferiority, marginalization and historical grievances still pervade some variants of the Igbo race. This is partly the reasons some Ikwere and Ika people would insist that they are everything other than Igbo.³¹ Within these two sub-ethnic groups of the nation, there is a growing sentiment of detachment from hinterland Igbo, which is why Ohaneze NdiIgbo, the apex socio-cultural group housing all Igbo people, have been making frantic efforts to see how it could reintegrate these sub-Igbo ethnic groups into a one big family. There is now a growing demand for the next leadership of Ohaneze Ndigbo to come from Ikwere as a pragmatic step towards Igbo unification. This course was recently achieved by the emergence of Sen. John Mbata as President General of the Igbo apex group.

I once served a boss who hails from Ika, Delta State. He often lamented and decried the attitude of his colleagues from mainstream Igbo states towards those of them from the non-fully-Igbo states. He lampooned the fact that the matter of Igbo-ness only comes up when it is convenient to do so. But when interest comes to play, the same people chorusing Igbo unity would turn around

³¹ Chimazuru Nnadi-Oforgu, "The Igbo Dilemma: A Self-Inflicted Identity Crisis" Available @<https://oblongmedia.net/2025> Retrieved 09/01/2025

and begin to discriminate between who is a real Igbo and who is not. This attitude is divisive and inimical to the quest for Igbo unity and solidarity. When home was home, the entire Igboland was home to every Igbo person before the artificial creation of states which pitched one state against the other with an evil concept introduced as indigeneship. People who share common ancestry, language and culture became divided by virtue of the state they belong, and this introduced rivalry rather than complementarity. The hinterland Igbo must resist the urge to dismember the Igbo race through setting highfalutin standards for acceptance into a full-blooded Igbo race. It is this same disingenuous systemic discrimination that is unwittingly replicated against the Igbo people within the Nigeria State whereby there is always a deliberate benchmark required for Igbo success. “And yet, we complain bitterly about those external injustices while replicating them internally”.³² The crux of the matter is that this calls for soul-searching, self-purgation and auto-correction.

Needless to say, also, that the Igbo possess both the resources and the workforce necessary to improve their homeland. The five states of the southeast region, in conjunction with their kith and kin in the neighbouring states, can convene a summit of their spiritual, traditional, political leaders and leaders of thought to brainstorm on ways to eliminate the underlying causes of unrest in Igbo territory in order to restore the dying glory of the heartland. It is doable with leadership with sincerity of purpose, in fact, in proffering practical solution for the enthronement of peace and tranquility as well as restoring the glory of the homeland, Egbujo submits: “The five states can form joint southeast development and security commissions. A joint consultative assembly can agree on a circular rail line around the Igbo nation. The bestowal of sub-national honours on Igbos who site factories and job-creating businesses in Igbo land can also begin. So that those who seek to brag can brag with the number of jobs they have created in Igbo land”.³³ In a similar vein, the entire Igbo race must wake up and eschew the ostrich attitude as though the enemy lies beyond reach. The race must understand the stake ahead and make intentional efforts at pulling its own together. The race is in dire need of cohesion, not fragmentation. To instill the feeling of belonging and ownership, the race requires cohesiveness and unity of purpose³⁴. It is then it can collectively address its challenges, most especially the

³² *ibid*

³³ *ibid*

³⁴ Isaac Igwe, “Sustaining the Culture of Participation and Peaceful Coexistence through the Inclusionist Approach to Diversity” in *Nigerian Journal of African Studies* vol. 3, N0.1 (Awka: African Studies Research, 2021), pp.34-35

identified threats to the cherished homecoming culture. Keeping the tenets of home consciousness should be a thing of pride for Igbos. The research therefore beckons on all and sundry to join hands in bringing back that peaceful ambience and place of refuge which the idea of home and homecoming truly invokes into the consciousness of the Igbo person.

WORKS CITED

- Ameh C. G. "Anyone that does not vote Ambode will be thrown into lagoon-Oba of Lagos warns Igbos." Daily Post 2015, April 6. Available at <https://dailypost.ng/2015/04/06>
- Balogun, T. Why Igbos Build Mansions: A Deep Dive on Marketing, Cultural Norms of Ndigbo." Available @ <https://brandcom.ng/2024/01/08/why-igbos-build-mansions-a-deep-dive-on-marketing-cultural-norms-of-ndigbo/>
- Coreth, E. *Metaphysics*. New York: Herder, 1968.
- Corgi, S. What is 'home': Personal Idea and Scholar's Approaches to the Definition of 'home'. November 11,2023. Retrieved from <https://studycorgi.com/what-is-home/>
- Egbujo, U. "The Igbo and Homecoming." Vanguard NewsPaper 2023, May 13. Available @<https://www.vanguardngr.com/2023/05/the-igbo-and-homecoming/>
- Falk, J. "The Role of Cultural Metaphysics in Psychological Theory." *Canadian Journal of Psychology* 1953; 7 (1). Available @<https://psycnet.apa.org/buy/1954-00044-001>
- Igwe, I.C. "Combating Radicalism and Violent Extremism in Local Communities: Perspectives and Practices." NARC JOURNAL 2021; 4(1). Abuja: Nigerian Army Resource Center.
- Igwe, I.C. "Sustaining the Culture of Participation and Peaceful Coexistence through the Inclusivist Approach to Diversity." *Nigerian Journal of African Studies* 2021; 3(1). Awka: African Studies Research.
- Iroegbu, p. *Metaphysics, the Kpim of Philosophy*. Owerri: International University Press, 1995.
- Kalu, A. "African Identity and the Emergence of Globalization." *American International Journal of Contemporary Research* 2013; 3(6).
- Madukasi, C. "Obu" The Sacred Homestead for Ancestral Veneration." *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science* 2021 5(1). Available at www.rsisinternational.org
- Mallett, S. "Understanding Home: A Critical Review of the Literature." *The Sociological Review* 52 (1). Melbourne: University of Melbourne, 2004.
- Margolis, J. *Towards a Metaphysics of Culture*, 1st Edition. London: Routledge, 2019.
- Mbiti, J.S. *African Religions and Philosophy*. London: Heinemann, 1985.

- Nnadi-Oforgu, C. “The Igbo Dilemma: A Self-Inflicted Identity Crisis.” Available @<https://oblongmedia.net/2025>
- Nwafor, I.M. “The living-dead (ancestors) among the Igbo-African people: An interpretation of Catholic sainthood.” *International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology* 2017; 9 (4). DOI: 10.5897/IJSA2017.0719
- Okoye C. and Ukanwa, O. “Igbo Traditional Architecture: A Symbol of Igbo Cultural Identity” *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research* 2019;10 (11). Available at <http://www.ijser.org>
- Onuegbu, C. “Travel: The Economics of Igbo Homecoming” 2017. Available @<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/travel-economics-igbo-homecoming-collins-onuegbu/>
- Onwuka, A. “How ‘Village’ has Harmed the Igbo People.” *The Punch Newspapers*, 9th January 2024. Available @https://punchng.com.translate.goog/how-village-has-harmed-the-igbo-people/?_x_tr_sl=en&_x_tr_tl=ig&_x_tr_hl=ig&_x_tr_pto=sc
- Unah, J. I. *Metaphysics*. Lagos: University of Lagos Press, 2010.

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Isaac Chidi Igwe, PhD is a Senior Lecturer at Department of Philosophy, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

Email: ic.igwe@unizik.edu.ng

Franklin Emenike Okamigbo is a Lecturer at Department of Philosophy, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

Email: frankokamigbo@yahoo.com